

NOTES

Formation Constants of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} Complexes of *m*-Mercaptoacetamidophenol (*m*-MAP)

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Received 4 March 1972

In continuation of our previous work¹ this communication deals with the determination of stepwise formation constants of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes with *m*-MAP employing Irving-Rossotti method².

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were either B.D.H. Analar or equivalent quality.

Standard solutions of the ligand and the metal salts were prepared in double distilled water.

pH of the solutions were measured by using 'Polymetron CL-41' pH-meter.

The experimental set up, procedure and method of calculation are the same as described in the previous communication³.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stepwise formation constants of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes with *m*-MAP were determined by Irving-Rossotti method². Since the reagent was insoluble in water, a ethanol-water mixture (1 : 1 v/v) was used as a solvent. A bulk electrolyte of $\mu(0.1M)$ sodium perchlorate was adopted to maintain constant ionic strength and reaction solutions were all thermostated at $20 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The pK^H value of the ligand, 8.89, as reported by Kakkar *et al.*¹ under the same experimental conditions, was used for the calculations of stepwise formation constants of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes with *m*-MAP.

The stepwise formation constants were determined from the values of \bar{n} and $p(A)$. The values of n and $p(A)$ were calculated by using the equations² :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V''' - V'')[N + E^\circ + T_L^\circ(y - \bar{n}_A)]}{(V^\circ + V'')\bar{n}_A T_M^\circ},$$

$$p[A] = \log \frac{1 + p^{kH} \left(\frac{1}{\text{anti log } B} \right)}{(T_L^\circ - T_M^\circ) \bar{n}}, \frac{V^\circ + V''}{V^\circ}.$$

The results obtained are recorded in Tables 1 and 2 (Fig. 1, 2).

TABLE 1

Stepwise formation constants of Co^{2+} -*m*-MAP

$T_L^\circ = 0.01M$ $\mu = 0.1M(NaClO_4)$ $T = 20 \pm 0.1^\circ$
 $T_M^\circ = 0.001M$ $N + E^\circ = 0.6280$

B	V''	V'''	$V''' - V''$	\bar{n}	$p(A)$
3.0	1.900	1.950	0.050	0.6050	7.8577
3.2	1.950	2.025	0.075	0.9067	7.6726
3.4	1.975	2.062	0.085	1.0270	7.4787
3.8	2.000	2.100	0.100	1.2080	7.0977
4.2	2.012	2.125	0.113	1.3650	6.6957
4.6	2.025	2.150	0.125	1.5222	6.3039
5.0	2.025	2.161	0.136	1.6290	5.9095
5.4	2.025	2.175	0.150	1.8110	5.5191

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

TABLE 2

Stepwise formation constants of Ni^{2+} -*m*-MAP

$T_L^\circ = 0.01M$ $\mu = 0.1M(NaClO_4)$ $T = 20 \pm 0.1^\circ$
 $T_M^\circ = 0.001M$ $N + E^\circ = 0.6280$

B	V''	V'''	$V''' - V''$	\bar{n}	$p(A)$
4.2	2.000	2.025	0.025	0.3019	6.6495
4.4	2.000	2.037	0.037	0.4469	6.4512
4.6	2.000	2.050	0.050	0.6039	6.2584
5.0	2.010	2.062	0.052	0.6279	5.8597
5.2	2.010	2.075	0.065	0.7848	5.6671
5.4	2.012	2.087	0.075	0.9057	5.4729
5.6	2.012	2.112	0.100	1.2080	5.2878
5.8	2.012	2.137	0.125	1.5100	5.1032
6.0	2.015	2.150	0.138	1.6666	4.9114
6.2	2.020	2.162	0.147	1.7750	4.7171
6.4	2.025	2.175	0.156	1.8830	4.5230
6.6	2.025	2.187	0.162	1.9555	4.3269

Formation curves were obtained by plotting \bar{n} against $p(\text{A})$ as given in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3

The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ were directly read from the formation curves and are recorded below :

Complex	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Co^{2+} - <i>m</i> MAP	8.74 ± 0.05	6.38 ± 0.06	15.04 ± 0.05
Ni^{2+} - <i>m</i> MAP	6.38 ± 0.03	5.10 ± 0.06	11.48 ± 0.08

The above results show that the stability order is $\text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+}$. This order of stability follows neither the Irving-William's rule⁴ nor any of the empirical orders reviewed by Irving and William⁴. The complete disagreement of the Irving-William's order in the present case may be attributed to stabilization by Jahn-Teller distortion for cobalt(II) complexes analogous to that of copper(II) complexes and the favourable entropy terms for cobalt(II) complexes as compared for nickel(II) complexes.

Authors' thanks are due to Prof. M. M. Bokadia, School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain, (M.P.), for providing necessary facilities to carry out this work.

REFERENCES

1. S. N. Kakkar, N. S. Poonia and P. V. Khadikar. Communicated.
2. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
3. P. V. Khadikar and R. L. Ameria, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (In press).
4. H. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746.

